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Deliverable D6.3 - Report on activities conducted to build on synergies

WP6 – Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation

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Partners short names / Legal name

APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
ATC	Athens Technology Center S.A.
CIMA	Centro Internazionale di Monitoraggio Ambientale – CIMA Foundation
CMCC	Euro – Mediterranean Center on Climate Change – CMCC Foundation
ECSA	Verein Der Europaeischen Buergerwissenschaften – ECSA E.v
IBE	Fundación Iberoicivis
ICLEI	ICLEI European Secretariat GMBH (ICLEI EUROPASEKRETARIAT GMBH)
IIASA	Internationales Institut fuer Angewandte Systemanalyse
SEI OX	Stockholm Environment Institute, Oxford Office Limited
SEI TAL	Sihtasutus Stockholmi Keskkonnainstituudi Tallinna Keskus
UNIGE	Université de Geneve

Abbreviation and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
BAMS	Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society
CEI	Citizen Engagement Initiative
Central European Time	CET
CPA	Climate Pact Ambassador
D	Deliverable
ECCA	European Climate Change Adaptation Conference
EEA	European Environment Agency
EDMO	European Digital Media Observatory
EU	European Union
EURESFO	European Urban Resilience Forum
GA	Grant Agreement
ICT	Information and Communication Tool

MIP4Adapt	Mission Implementation Platform for Adaptation
NGO	Non-governmental Organisation
PLW	Peer-Learning Workshop
Q&A	Question and Answer
T	Task
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

This report showcases the results from the activities carried out to establish, build and leverage partnerships with the mapped national, European Union (EU) and international projects and citizen engagement initiatives (including projects funded under the same Mission), as well as projects identified in Task (T) 1.1 where citizen engagement initiatives were identified. During the reporting period, the Adaptation AGORA project ran several key activities to build stronger connections between consortium partners, research groups, policy networks, and community stakeholders. These efforts aimed to make the most of everyone's expertise, encourage shared learning, and keep climate adaptation work aligned across Europe and nearby regions.

Joint workshops, themed roundtables, and collaborative research sessions brought together scientists, policymakers, and practitioners, while shared online platforms made it easier to exchange methods, data, and good practices. This joined-up approach has improved coordination, cut down on duplicated work, and set the stage for more effective and inclusive adaptation strategies. The results of these joint efforts show how valuable a collaborative approach can be in supporting the Horizon Europe goals.

Partners have created shared knowledge products, contributed to policy recommendations, and built stronger links with other EU-funded projects, helping to raise the project's profile and impact. The experience underlines how important ongoing collaboration and open sharing of knowledge are for driving real progress on climate adaptation. Looking ahead, the project will keep strengthening partnerships, putting long-term cooperation structures in place, and finding new opportunities for joint work and knowledge exchange ensuring that Adaptation AGORA stays an active and inclusive space for building climate resilience.

This report is organised to provide a clear overview of the activities implemented to build on synergies within the Adaptation AGORA Horizon Project. Section 2 sets out the background and objectives of Work Package 6 (WP6), as well as the specific aims of this deliverable, providing the contextual framework for the activities described. Section 3 details the range of synergy activities undertaken, including webinars, peer-learning workshops, and the final conference, together with additional collaborative actions that enhanced coordination among partners. Finally, Section 4 compiles the annexes, offering supporting materials and documentation relevant to the activities reported.

2. Background

2.1 Work Package 6 objectives

WP6 aimed to ensure the effective dissemination and uptake of Adaptation AGORA outputs and results to targeted audiences (including entities external to the consortium), raising awareness and informing the large public about them. It established synergies, opportunities for collaboration and joint actions with other projects, initiatives and activities.

The activities carried out to engage stakeholders and share the results from the project's activities throughout the whole duration of the project served as a starting point to connect with each of the target audiences. Additionally, during these three years other EU-funded projects were being developed in complementary areas, where the results from one another could be leveraged and contribute to enrich the tasks developed.

Because of this, adequate engagement and participation in other projects' events was deemed a key aspect of the communication and dissemination plan and subsequent strategy. In Deliverable (D) 6.4, the details as to how this was addressed are outlined. Similarly, the outputs of the Adaptation AGORA project can benefit initiatives that have been approved and are currently being deployed, such as Horizon Europe TICCA4DANU project. In D6.4, as well as in D6.5, which constitutes the Exploitation strategy, these are further explained.

With the support from WP7 (Project Management) and WP8 (Ethics) these opportunities were mapped and identified. Additionally, the EU Mission Implementation Platform (MIP4Adapt) was also used as a channel to showcase the partial results from Adaptation AGORA and gaining the attention from other EU projects to establish new synergies. The participation in the Thematic Working Groups served as another mechanism to get to know in more detail the activities being carried out by projects under the same call or complementary areas, once again expanding the links and outreach.

2.2 Deliverable 6.3 objectives

This report provides an overview of the activities related to T6.3, which aimed to foster synergies with mapped national, European, and international projects and citizen engagement initiatives, including those funded under the same Mission (e.g. HORIZON-MISS-2021-OCEAN-05-03).

Partners established collaborations with the European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO), its regional hubs, and other Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects addressing the specific challenge of disinformation. Through these collaborations annual peer-learning workshops (led by BSC) were carried out to encourage knowledge exchange and identify opportunities for joint action. Based on the results from these workshops, specific events were co-organized to address the opportunities identified.

In addition, three thematic webinars have been delivered, jointly with other projects, to promote citizens' engagement in climate change mitigation and adaptation. The three webinars were conceived as a coherent series illustrating how effective climate adaptation emerges from the interaction between science, systems, and society. The first explored participatory processes and citizen science, emphasising the role of communities in observing and understanding climate impacts. The second focused on water sustainability, linking global research and regional challenges to the need for informed, citizen-supported adaptation strategies. The third showcased practical governance models from Adaptation AGORA and CLIMAS, demonstrating how Climate Assemblies, Living Labs, and local engagement can co-create evidence-based solutions. Together, the webinars highlight that successful adaptation requires informed citizens, resilient resource systems, and collaborative decision-making.

A joint final event, entitled "Citizens Together for Climate Adaptation", has been organised in collaboration with other relevant projects. This event will showcase diverse approaches to involving citizens in climate action and will convene key stakeholders, including Climate Pact Ambassadors (CPA).

3. Synergy activities

Several events were directly organized by Adaptation AGORA during the project to create strong connections between the consortium partners and other projects working on similar topics. To reach this objective, Adaptation AGORA organized 3 webinars (section 3.1), 4 peer-learning workshops (PLW) (section 3.2) and a final event (section 3.3). However, the networking activity was not limited to these events, in fact other initiatives (section 3.4) involving citizens and different stakeholders enriched the events portfolio of the project.

3.1 Webinars

Adaptation AGORA relied extensively on a structured series of webinars to fulfil its core objectives of co-creation and knowledge dissemination. These events went beyond simple information sharing, acting as vital platforms for stakeholder engagement and dialogue transferring specialized knowledge and closing the gap between science and practice. Each webinar addressed critical themes such as climate change adaptation, energy poverty, urban heat vulnerability, and combating disinformation. Through peer-to-peer exchanges and technical sessions, the project ensured that expert insights and lessons learned were promptly accessible to practitioners and policymakers across Europe.

3.1.1 Webinar 1: Processi partecipativi e cambiamento climatico. Il contributo dei cittadini durante le attività outdoor

Topic

The title of the webinar was “Processi partecipativi e cambiamento climatico – Il contributo dei cittadini durante le attività outdoor” (“Participatory Processes and Climate Change – The Contribution of Citizens during Outdoor Activities”). The title itself reflected the main objective of the event: to encourage citizen engagement with climate change issues and to highlight how their participation in outdoor activities can help in understanding and monitoring climate change.

The webinar began with a brief introduction to the Adaptation AGORA project and its objectives, followed by an explanation of the concept of “climate” and a presentation of the key issues related to climate change and possible future scenarios.

In the second part of the session, the concept of citizen science was introduced. The speaker explained how citizens can actively contribute to the understanding and monitoring of climate change, and several real-life examples of citizen science initiatives from previous projects were showcased.

The webinar was first organised on 29 January 2024 (Figure 1), but we were forced to interrupt it due to a hacking incident. During the presentation a hacker disturbed the event (audio and video), and the external technical support could not remove this individual from the session. The logistical part of the event was handled by CentroLingue, providing the management of the Zoom platform and the simultaneous translation service under contract between APRE and CentroLingue. The main administrator provided limited co-administration rights to Antonio Parodi (speaker), to allow the sharing of video and audio content.

All the other participants only had the right to write on the zoom chat. All the microphones and videos were muted/locked when the webinar started. However, an external user joined the call sharing inappropriate content and to limit exposure to potential cybersecurity risks, the webinar was stopped and the cyberhacking protocols were implemented, ensuring no personal data had been compromised. New protocols were developed following the forensic report and the greater risks that Zoom posed, applicable to any future webinars directly organized by Adaptation AGORA, which can be found in Annex

The event was then re-scheduled for 15 April 2024 (Figure 2), from 16:00 to 17:30 Central European Time (CET), on Microsoft Teams. Antonio Parodi, senior researcher at the CIMA Research Foundation, delivered this webinar where he introduced key climate concepts and highlighted how citizen participation and outdoor activities can contribute to monitoring and understanding climate change. His intervention provided a scientific yet accessible foundation for the session, reinforcing the project’s emphasis on citizen engagement as a crucial component of effective climate adaptation.

Figure 1. Advertisement of the first webinar “Processi partecipativi e cambiamento climatico. Il contributo dei cittadini durante le attività outdoor” (closed for hacking).

Figure 2. Advertisement of the second webinar “Processi partecipativi e cambiamento climatico. Il contributo dei cittadini durante le attività outdoor” (re-organized).

Participants and stakeholders

Total number of registered participants: 192

Total number of attendees: 88

Three types of audiences were mainly represented during the webinar:

- Outdoor activity associations/companies (such as runners, bikers, trekkers, climbers ...)
- Public entities environmental offices
- Natural parks managers.

Methodology of engagement/invitation

The webinar was promoted via the Adaptation AGORA website, Adaptation AGORA social media channels, the social media pages of Adaptation AGORA partners (Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn), partners' newsletters, and direct email invitations sent from the Adaptation AGORA email account. As the webinar targeted associations and companies involved in outdoor activities, nearly 400 direct invitations were issued to representatives of:

- Runners' associations,
- Cyclists' associations,
- Trekking associations/companies (including Club Alpino Italiano and the Federazione Italiana Trekker),
- Environmental associations,
- Environmental education centres,
- Natural parks,
- Regional and municipal authorities that have previously organised events on climate change adaptation.

The webinar was conducted in Italian for an Italian stakeholder audience. A Microsoft Forms registration form was created and kept open for two weeks. An invitation letter, prepared in two versions for new contacts and for stakeholders previously engaged by Adaptation AGORA, was shared by email. The meeting link was sent in a separate email a few days before the event, which also served as a reminder.

Immediately before and during the webinar, potential participants contacted the Adaptation AGORA team by email to request access; however, they were unable to join due to security settings. Email accounts had to be carefully verified to prevent unwanted attendees (e.g., hackers).

Format and methodology

The webinar followed a structured format, featuring a moderator (Riccardo Biondi) and a speaker (Antonio Parodi). The moderator opened the session by introducing the topic and explaining how participants could interact with the speaker. The speaker delivered the presentation with the support of a PowerPoint slideshow.

At the end of the presentation, participants were invited to ask questions using the Question and Answer (Q&A) tool in Microsoft Teams. The moderator read the questions aloud, and the speaker provided the answers (Figure 3). The speaker's email address was shared with participants to enable them to follow up with further questions after the official conclusion of the meeting.

Figure 3. Discussion during the webinar.

Discussion and feedback

Figure 4. Screenshot of the Q&A.

The Q&A session was highly engaging (Figure 4), and the webinar received very positive feedback from participants. Two main audience groups were represented: associations and companies involved in outdoor activities (such as running, cycling, trekking, and climbing), and environmental offices from public institutions.

Questions from the outdoor activity associations and companies mainly focused on the technical aspects of the MeteoTrackers, including their cost, applicability in different environments, reliability, and the extent to which they can genuinely enhance climate monitoring and support climate change adaptation efforts.

Representatives of public institutions were particularly interested in understanding whether low-cost sensors could also be used for air quality monitoring, and whether they could take part in ongoing citizen science activities — potentially extending these initiatives to other regions.

Further feedback was received by email following the webinar, with participants requesting additional information, materials such as the PowerPoint presentation, and contact details. One of the most discussed topics was the potential application of MeteoTrackers during hikes and excursions, particularly when attached to bicycles or backpacks. Several public entities expressed interest in becoming directly involved in ongoing citizen science activities and joining the AGORA network for future collaboration opportunities.

In the week following the webinar, participants were also given the opportunity to request a certificate of participation. A total of 20 certificates were issued upon request. The detailed record of the Q&A session is included in the Annex.

Material availability

On the website of Adaptation AGORA, it is possible to find the recording of the webinar and the presentation of Dr. Antonio Parodi:

<https://adaptationagora.eu/1st-agora-webinar-participatory-processes-and-climate-change-the-contribution-of-citizens-during-outdoor-activities/>

Moreover, the webinar is also available on Adaptation AGORA YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZzcS4ux3CI8&t=67s>

3.1.2 Webinar 2: Water's Sustainability: how to ensure our future?

Topic

Most impacts of climate change directly affect water resources — from extreme events such as floods and droughts to the shrinking of ice sheets and rising sea levels. Consequently, accurately assessing these risks, developing effective adaptation strategies, and engaging citizens are essential to ensuring the sustainability of water sources worldwide.

The webinar was organised to deepen understanding of the challenges posed by climate change to water systems through a multidisciplinary approach, exploring how these issues are being addressed from global research, regional, and transboundary perspectives.

The webinar was organised on 19 September 2024, from 17:30 to 19:00 CET. In this case, given that the webinar was co-organized by Adaptation AGORA and the MI4Adapt, the Mission took over the coordination, setup, registration and platform hosting activities. Because of this, the webinar took place on the Mission’s platform, following their webinar protocols.

The webinar featured five speakers selected for their complementary expertise across research, governance, industry, and youth engagement. Dionisio Pérez Blanco and Marina Mattera (CMCC) provided solid scientific and socio-institutional perspectives on water and climate adaptation, while Mauricio Serra (OAS) contributed an international governance viewpoint on transboundary water challenges. Rosario Arnau (IWA - YWP Spain) brought the voice of young professionals, highlighting innovation and capacity building, and Mar Micò (Acciona) offered practical insights from the private sector on sustainable water management solutions. Together, their contributions ensured relevance for the project’s diverse target audiences and stakeholders, demonstrating the need for coordinated, multi-actor collaboration to secure water sustainability under climate change.

Figure 5. Advertisement of the webinar “Water’s sustainability: how to ensure our future?”.

Participants and stakeholders

Total number of registered participants: 287

Total number of attendees: 62

Three types of audiences were mainly represented during the webinar: partners of EU-funded projects from various programmes working on adaptation, academy, and private sector stakeholders. Here the detail:

- Mission Projects: EU-funded projects from various programmes working on adaptation: 10
- Other: 19

- Private sector: 9
- Friend of the Mission: 9
- Charter Signatory: 4
- Non-profit: 4
- Regions and Local Authorities participating in projects: 3
- OAS collaborator: 2

Methodology of engagement/invitation

The event was part of the Adaptation AGORA webinar series, which aims to foster knowledge sharing and strengthen networking among projects and stakeholders engaged in water sustainability and climate adaptation.

The invitation was disseminated through the AGORA website, newsletters, and social media channels, as well as via the Mission Adaptation Community of Practice managed by MIP4Adapt.

Participants registered through an online form and joined the session via Microsoft Teams. The webinar was recorded, and Slido was used to facilitate an interactive Q&A session with the audience.

Format and methodology

The session began with a welcome. The host (Marina Mattera CMCC) thanked everyone for attending the webinar on Water Sustainability, which aimed to explore how to secure our future through diverse perspectives and stakeholder experiences. Participants were encouraged to post questions through Slido. The webinar featured five key presentations, followed by an interactive Q&A session moderated via Slido. The speakers represented a range of perspectives, spanning scientific research, policy, and youth engagement:

1. Risk Assessment and Adaptation Strategies (Dionisio Pérez Blanco, CMCC). Dionisio Pérez Blanco highlighted the shift from traditional water supply expansion to demand management using economic instruments and nature-based solutions. He stressed integrating economic and hydrological models, transparent communication of uncertainties, and capacity-building between scientists and policymakers.
2. Citizen Engagement and the Adaptation AGORA Project (Marina Mattera CMCC). The project promotes citizen participation in climate adaptation across four European cities. Surveys in Spain showed willingness to engage but low trust in authorities. Transparent communication and visible policy impact are key to maintaining engagement, especially during crises.
3. Transboundary Water Management (Mauricio Serra, Organisation of American States). Mauricio Serra discussed OAS efforts in managing shared water resources across Latin

America. Projects focus on governance, capacity-building, and climate resilience. Collaboration, data sharing, and integrated basin management are crucial for sustainable transboundary cooperation.

4. Youth Engagement (Rosario Arnau, International Water Association - YWP Spain). Rosario Arnau presented YWP Spain's work in building a network of young water professionals. Initiatives include mentoring, citizen science, and school outreach. Engagement is strongest when young people co-create projects rather than being passive participants.
5. Private Sector Innovation in Water Management (Mar Micò, Acciona). Mar Micò showcased Acciona's transformation of wastewater plants into bio factories for resource recovery. EU regulations and sustainability goals drive innovation. Key challenges include governance gaps and creating markets for recovered materials.

Discussion and feedback

To close the session, Martina Álvarez from the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change invited participants to join the Community of Practice hosted on the Mission Implementation Platform. The community organises open events, peer learning programmes, and matchmaking sessions for regions and projects working on adaptation. She encouraged attendees to scan the QR code and register to stay involved in ongoing initiatives.

The webinar ended with an invitation to continue collaboration and knowledge exchange among all stakeholders. Participants expressed strong interest in the multidisciplinary nature of the event, appreciating the combination of scientific, policy, and youth perspectives. Several attendees raised questions concerning the economic instruments presented by CMCC, the methodology employed for the Catalonia drought survey, and potential opportunities for future collaboration among Mission projects.

The feedback emphasised the importance of promoting water literacy, strengthening trust between citizens and institutions, and empowering younger generations to take an active role in climate adaptation efforts. The following questions were asked (the answer was sent by email):

- @Carlos, how do you include the positionality of the modeller. This influences model outcomes. e.g. too much emphasis on RS may negate groundwater.
- @Marina, have you carried out any activities with other groups of citizens, besides Millennials?
- @Mar, can you explain a bit further how AI can be introduced in water treatment and do you think it can help companies collaborate with regular citizens?

Material availability

The recording and presentations were made available through the Adaptation AGORA YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=x-Ai0b3b2G0>

3.1.3 Webinar 3: Citizen engagement in climate adaptation processes: lessons learned from Adaptation AGORA and CLIMAS' experiences

Topic

The webinar focused on citizen engagement as a key driver of effective climate adaptation, highlighting how participatory approaches can strengthen both the legitimacy and the impact of adaptation strategies. To reinforce this perspective, Adaptation AGORA has established synergies with the EU Mission on Adaptation and the CLIMAS project.

These collaborations ensure that the project's activities align with wider European priorities and benefit from shared expertise. The Mission provides a strategic framework and a Community of Practice that supports regions and communities in advancing their adaptation capacities, while CLIMAS contributes complementary methodologies, including Climate Assemblies and Living Labs, that demonstrate how deliberative democracy and citizen science can generate co-created, evidence-based policy recommendations.

Together, these partnerships enhance the relevance of Adaptation AGORA's work by offering stakeholders coherent guidance, tested tools and access to European-wide learning. During the webinar, Adaptation AGORA presented its approach to promoting active community participation in adaptation processes, emphasising collaboration between citizens, institutions and local actors. The project applies multidisciplinary methods to develop adaptation solutions that are effective, sustainable and grounded in societal needs. CLIMAS complemented this perspective by illustrating participatory governance models that help communities deliberate on climate challenges and contribute directly to policy formulation.

Pilot cases from both projects showcased how citizen engagement can address diverse climate risks across Europe. These included:

- tackling water scarcity, heat stress and desertification in Aragón (Spain);
- strengthening local adaptation capacity in Rome (Italy);
- responding to urban heat vulnerability in Malmö (Sweden);
- building awareness and resilience to floods and heatwaves in Dresden (Germany);
- further examples from Edermünde, Riga and Catalunya demonstrated how deliberative Climate Assemblies can inform decisions on land use and urban greening.

Across all cases, the shared objective was clear: to empower communities to co-design adaptation measures that reflect local priorities and challenges, ensuring that climate action is both context-specific and socially supported.

The webinar was organised on 9 April 2025, from 17:30 to 19:00 CET, using the Zoom platform (Figure 6) as once again this event was co-organized with the MI4Adapt and the Mission’s webinar protocols were followed and they acted as platform hosts.

Figure 6. Advertisement of the webinar “Citizen engagement in climate adaptation processes: lessons learned from Adaptation AGORA and CLIMAS’ experiences”.

Participants and stakeholders

Total number of registered participants: 519

Total number of attendees: 182

Three types of audiences were mainly represented during the webinar: non-profit organizations, partners of EU-funded projects from various programmes working on adaptation, and friends of the mission. Here the detail:

- Non-profit: 57
- Mission Projects: EU-funded projects from various programmes working on adaptation: 45
- Friend of the Mission: 23
- Private sector: 17
- Regions and Local Authorities participating in projects: 12
- Other EU Mission Representative and/or participant: 11
- Charter Signatory: 5
- Climate PACT Ambassadors: 4

- Member State representatives in other countries/regions: 3
- Member State representatives in the EU: 3
- EU Regional and national adaptation Platforms: 2

Methodology of engagement/invitation

The webinar was organised within the framework of the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change and its Community of Practice, coordinated by MIP4Adapt. The event brought together representatives from EU Mission projects, local and regional authorities, national contact points, and European institutions to share practical experiences on citizen engagement in climate adaptation.

Participants included Adaptation AGORA and CLIMAS project partners, as well as pilot and assembly representatives from Rome, Zaragoza, Malmö, Dresden, Catalunya, Riga, and Edermünde. The invitation targeted a broad audience of mission participants and stakeholders involved in adaptation policy, research, and citizen participation.

Information was disseminated through the Mission Adaptation Portal, newsletters, and social media channels (@MIP4Adapt). Attendees were encouraged to join the Community of Practice to continue exchanging knowledge and contributing to ongoing mission activities.

Format and methodology

The webinar was moderated by Martina Alvarez, representative of MIP4Adapt (Mission Implementation Platform for Adaptation to Climate Change), supporting the EU Mission on Adaptation through capacity building, peer learning and community engagement.

The online session was structured as a series of presentations followed by a Q&A session moderated via Slido, ensuring interaction and equal opportunity for participants to ask questions.

The format followed a case-based methodology, combining institutional overviews, project presentations, and practical pilot case studies. Each presentation illustrated a different participatory approach implemented under Horizon Europe projects Adaptation AGORA and CLIMAS.

Speakers represented both the coordination teams and pilot sites, highlighting participatory processes such as inception workshops, focus groups, and co-creation workshops. These activities aimed to identify local barriers and vulnerabilities, co-develop adaptation solutions, and integrate citizens' contributions into policy and planning frameworks. The list of speakers with relative talk is the following:

- Paola Mercogliano (CMCC), Adaptation Agorà Project Leader
- Judith Bielsa (Fundación Ibercivis), "Citizen engagement in the Region of Aragón, Spain"
- Marta Ellena (CMCC), "Citizen engagement experiences and outcomes from the City of Rome, Italy"

- Mathilda Englund (SEI HQ and Linköping University), “Citizen engagement in Malmö, Sweden”
- Anna Verones (ECSA), “Citizen engagement in Dresden, Germany”
- Rebecca Hueting (Deep Blue Italy), CLIMAS Communication leader
- Ariana Apine (Zala Briviba/Green Liberty), “Climate Assembly Riga, Latvia”

Discussion and feedback

The presentations and subsequent discussion highlighted several cross-cutting findings and reflections emerging from the pilots and assemblies:

- Diverse participation proved essential to ensure representativeness, engaging decision-makers, youth, workers, multi-ethnic communities, and vulnerable groups such as seniors and people with disabilities.
- Local relevance strongly influenced engagement outcomes. Rural participants prioritised fire prevention, water management, and climate-resilient crops, while urban actors focused on communication, heat adaptation, and infrastructure resilience.
- Trust-building and dialogue emerged as key enablers for effective engagement, fostering mutual learning between citizens, experts, and local institutions.
- Education and awareness were consistently identified as fundamental to long-term resilience, with recommendations for environmental education programmes and school-based activities.
- Integration into policy was successfully demonstrated in several contexts — notably in Malmö, where Adaptation AGORA findings were endorsed by local authorities and incorporated into planning for the Urban Heat Strategy, and in Riga, where citizen recommendations contributed to the Urban Greening Plan 2027–2031.

From a methodological standpoint, the event underlined the need to:

- Maintain flexibility in applying engagement tools across different local contexts.
- Ensure informed and inclusive participation to enable balanced deliberation.
- Simplify administrative and institutional procedures to accelerate adaptation implementation.
- Provide continuity mechanisms to sustain citizen involvement beyond the project cycle.

Participants agreed that getting citizens involved is essential for achieving real and lasting progress in climate adaptation. They highlighted that the participatory approaches developed through the Adaptation AGORA and CLIMAS projects offer practical models that can be replicated across different regions in Europe.

The full Q&A session is included in the Annex; overall the discussion focused on citizen engagement, stakeholder collaboration, and methods for climate adaptation within the two projects. Participants asked about project logistics, engagement strategies, and how to balance adaptation and mitigation. The organisers explained that activities were carried out in several cities, usually with about six months between workshops, and that citizens took part throughout — from the first consultations to the final discussions.

Stakeholders were identified using the MapStakes tool, which helped ensure a wide mix of participants, legitimacy, and inclusion of multicultural groups. No financial incentives were offered; people joined based on their own interest and commitment. The discussion also touched on the use of local and traditional knowledge, how to validate workshop results, and the creation of tools and protocols for multilingual engagement.

On a broader level, the Q&A showed strong interest in long-term sustainability, policy impact, and empowering citizens. The Malmö pilot was mentioned as continuing beyond project funding, while Rome's findings were included in the city's Climate Strategy. Other questions explored the role of digital tools, citizen science, and education in preparing future professionals.

The session ended with reflections on citizen assemblies, stressing the importance of government accountability, transparent follow-up, and the role of NGOs and media in keeping momentum going. Overall, the discussion showed a participatory and knowledge-driven approach to climate adaptation — one that connects science, communities, and policy innovation.

Material availability

Slides and webinar are available on

<https://adaptationagora.eu/citizen-engagement-in-climate-adaptation-processes-lessons-learned-from-adaptation-agora-and-climas-experiences/>

3.1.4 Overall Conclusions: Contribution of the Webinar Series to the Project

Taken together, the three webinars formed a coherent learning and engagement pathway that supported the overall objectives of the project and strengthened dialogue with a wide range of stakeholders. The first webinar introduced participatory processes and citizen science as entry points for engaging communities in understanding climate change, grounding scientific concepts in everyday outdoor experiences. The second webinar focused on water sustainability, connecting climate impacts on a critical resource with scientific analysis, governance perspectives, youth engagement and private-sector solutions. The third webinar brought these elements together by demonstrating how citizen engagement can be embedded in climate adaptation governance through structured participatory approaches, drawing on concrete experiences from Adaptation AGORA, CLIMAS and the EU Mission on Adaptation.

Collectively, the webinar series enabled the project to engage diverse stakeholder groups—including researchers, public authorities, international organisations, private-sector actors, civil society and young professionals—within a shared framework. Additionally, it served as a direct channel for new target audiences to learn about Adaptation AGORA, thus expanding the interest and areas of applicability of the results obtained in the project. By combining scientific knowledge, practical case studies and participatory methodologies, the webinars facilitated knowledge exchange, fostered mutual understanding across sectors and highlighted the value of collaboration in addressing climate risks.

As a result, the series contributed to raising awareness, strengthening networks and reinforcing the project's role as a platform for dialogue and learning on citizen-centred climate adaptation across Europe.

3.2 Peer-learning workshops

As part of its dissemination strategy (T6.3), Adaptation AGORA organized a series of peer-learning workshops designed to promote intensive knowledge exchange and identify opportunities for collaboration with other relevant projects. Three workshops were held, serving as key platforms for mutual learning—enabling the project to both share insights and draw lessons from existing participatory and deliberative processes. The peer learning workshops played a crucial role in addressing the topics covered in WP1 and they represent a strict connection between WP1 and WP6. These workshops engaged internal consortium members to refine approaches for involving policymakers and citizens, as well as external stakeholders to ensure project outcomes were communicated effectively while fostering joint actions and partnerships. They provided key opportunities to gather insights from the Adaptation AGORA network and the broader community, serving as an essential component for data collection, showcasing progress, and validating emerging results.

The first peer-learning workshop identified engagement practices contributing to the four pillars of the evaluation framework (T3.2) and examined whether stakeholder-focused practices could also be applied to citizens. The second peer learning workshop was a continuation of the first as an interactive in person event. The third workshop was organized during the European Urban Resilience Forum (EURESFO) 2024 conference, exploring how to design engagement activities within real-world case studies from Adaptation AGORA pilots and the ACCTING project. Finally, the last peer learning workshop served to validate all the findings of the previous meetings.

3.2.1 Peer-learning workshop 1

Topic

Presenters were asked to focus on stakeholder engagement broadly, including coproduction processes where citizens were not directly involved. The guiding questions explored the evolution of collective knowledge: where we started, what we learned during the first year of the project, and how we aim to further develop our understanding of Citizen Engagement Initiatives (CEIs) in the future.

The meeting was held online via Microsoft Teams on 24 November 2023. All details are available in Adaptation AGORA D1.2.

Participants and stakeholders

Total number of participants: 16

Methodology of engagement/invitation

An open invitation was sent to the Adaptation AGORA community to attend an online workshop. By including presentations on the different groups working on engagement in the agenda, it was hoped that the collective group would have a broad understanding of different engagement perspectives.

Format and methodology

The core content presented below stems from a series of facilitated, interactive workshops. During these sessions, participants worked in parallel groups to identify practices implemented at various stages of engagement, each aimed at achieving specific objectives.

The meeting began with presentations from Adaptation AGORA groups leading engagement research and practice. These presentations helped set the context and introduced the broader group to existing knowledge, including best practices from literature, experiences from Adaptation AGORA's four pilot regions, and policy-level barriers and enablers for engagement.

After the presentations, participants selected a "team" to join, each focused on a specific CEIs goal. This approach was designed to avoid the generalizations often found in literature. The four goals, based on the Adaptation AGORA Evaluation Framework, were:

1. Producing relevant knowledge and action tailored to local needs
2. Ensuring fair representation and participation
3. Fostering mutual learning
4. Enhancing collaboration

Drawing on findings from the literature review—which highlighted that engagement outcomes are shaped by activities, methods, and decisions across three main phases, and influenced by the CEI's context and purpose—we structured the discussion into four sequential sections:

1. Context and purpose of the CEI
2. Pre-engagement (planning and preparation)
3. Engagement day (execution of activities)
4. Post-engagement (evaluation and follow-up)

Each team was asked to provide examples of effective or ineffective practices for each phase that would support or hinder their specific goal. Discussions were actively facilitated, with 10–15 minutes allocated per phase, and responses were collected on an online whiteboard.

Due to lower-than-expected attendance, we opted to split the group between only the first two teams to ensure a diversity of perspectives. By the end of the first online workshop, we had gathered suggested practices for two of the four goals. It was agreed that contributions for the remaining goals would be added individually or asynchronously before the second meeting.

Discussion and feedback

The first peer-learning workshop produced a set of good and poor practices for citizen engagement, applicable at various stages of the engagement process. These practices were designed to either support or hinder the achievement of the four foundational pillars that define an “effective” CEI within the project.

This revised collection of good practices aligned with the four CEI pillars, however many practices and groupings still contained notable repetition. Therefore, we further synthesized the content to create a concise summary of good practices, which was the input for the second peer learning workshop.

Material availability

Paper in the Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society (BAMS) Meeting Summary <https://journals.ametsoc.org/view/journals/bams/105/12/BAMS-D-24-0172.1.xml?rskey=UA8M1q&result=1>

Adaptation AGORA D1.2 <https://adaptationagora.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/Deliverable-D1.2-Report-on-the-methodologies-and-recommendations-used-for-citizen-engagement.pdf>

3.2.2 Peer-learning workshop 2

Topic

After collecting 229 of practices for engaging stakeholders the aim of this meeting was to use the Adaptation AGORA General Assembly (GA) in Zaragoza to convert the stakeholder-relevant practices to citizen-relevant practices. This meeting – a continuation of the work carried out during the PLW 1 – was held in person in January 2024 in Zaragoza during the Adaptation AGORA GA. All details are available in Adaptation AGORA D1.2.

Participants and stakeholders

Total number of participants: 34

Methodology of engagement/invitation

By holding the workshop as a standalone session at the GA, we were able to involve all attending members of the Adaptation AGORA community that were present. The workshop was highly interactive and thus we decided to run it as an in-person only event. It was related to PLW1 but was also designed to be inclusive for people who had not attended the previous event.

Format and methodology

Before the meeting we collected 229 practices for engaging stakeholders via the online whiteboards used in the PLW1. The editing of the responses revealed significant repetition and many practices that might be better aligned with different goals or stages of engagement. To address this, the in-person meeting began with a sorting exercise. Participants were again divided into teams based on the four Adaptation AGORA project goals, but this time with a deliberate mix of individuals from different project areas and partner institutions. Each team received printed copies of the practices relevant to their assigned goal, organized by engagement stage. These were presented on removable cards lightly affixed to boards.

Teams were asked to complete three tasks:

1. **Goal Alignment:** Determine whether each practice was most relevant to their assigned goal or better suited to another. Practices deemed more appropriate for another goal were passed to the corresponding team. While this process was generally straightforward, a few practices circulated between teams, indicating potential relevance to multiple goals.
2. **Stage Classification:** Identify the most appropriate stage of the engagement process for each practice—whether retained or received from other teams—and group similar or duplicate entries. This resulted in a second, more refined version of stakeholder engagement practices.
3. **Citizen Relevance Assessment:** Evaluate each practice for its applicability to citizen engagement. Teams categorized practices as:
 - Directly relevant
 - Relevant with modifications
 - Not relevant.

Discussion and feedback

The workshop resulted in a refined series of good poor practices for citizen engagement, applicable at various stages of the engagement journey. These practices were designed to either support or hinder the achievement of the four core pillars that define an “effective” CEI within the Adaptation AGORA project. Most practices focused on stakeholder engagement were deemed transferable to citizen engagement. However, some participants highlighted the importance of treating citizens as a distinct group, requiring more tailored approaches that consider their specific needs and capacities.

After the workshop, the collected responses were refined to streamline the proposed guidelines. Recognizing that many good and bad practices were conceptually linked—often as direct opposites—we converted the negative examples into constructive recommendations (e.g., replacing “lack of resources” with “ensure sufficient resources”). These suggestions were then edited for clarity and compiled, while maintaining their original association with specific goals and stages.

The list of good practices is a living document that we have continued to develop via further engagement with the Adaptation AGORA community, an online expert survey, key informant interviews, an online webinar, and presentations at academic and stakeholder meetings.

Material availability

Paper in BAMS <https://journals.ametsoc.org/view/journals/bams/105/12/BAMS-D-24-0172.1.xml?rskey=UA8M1q&result=1>

Adaptation AGORA D1.2 <https://adaptationagora.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/Deliverable-D1.2-Report-on-the-methodologies-and-recommendations-used-for-citizen-engagement.pdf>

3.2.2 Peer-learning workshop 3

Topic

Local governments design and implementation of citizen engagement in climate resilience/adaptation involving the most vulnerable groups in society. Meaningful and effective citizen engagement considering substantial resource constraints imposed on local governments.

The meeting was held during the EURESFO24 on 27 of June 2024. The Forum featured five case studies from Malmö, Dresden, Rome, Messina, and Utrecht, facilitated by local experts and informed by the projects Adaptation AGORA, UrbanReLeaf, and ACCTING projects. Participants shared challenges, strategies, and best practices to ensure inclusive participation in co-creating local adaptation solutions, providing consistency to the activity performed during the webinars and peer learning workshops.

The event served as an opportunity to connect with other projects focused on citizen engagement in climate adaptation, to bring together diverse local and regional governments, and to begin a peer network continuing in the future.

Participants and stakeholders

Total number of participants: 70

Methodology of engagement/invitation

The workshop was organised as part of the program of the EURESFO24, co-organised by ICLEI Europe and the European Environment Agency (EEA), in the framework of the Valencia Cities Climate Week, together with the Cities Mission Conference and the Energy Cities' Annual Forum, hosted by the city as part of the Valencia EU Green Capital 2024 celebrations. The event was a unique opportunity to bring together representatives of cities and regions from across Europe to discuss challenges and opportunities for strengthening resilience in the wider context of sustainable urban development.

Participants of the workshop included representatives from Adaptation AGORA, Urban ReLeaf and ACCTING projects. The invitation targeted a broad audience of local and regional government officials, policy makers, practitioners, researchers and stakeholders involved in climate adaptation and citizen engagement. Information was disseminated through the project channels, the ICLEI Europe channels and the EURESFO24 official communication campaign.

Format and methodology

The workshop, co-organized together with the Urban ReLeaf and the ACCTING projects, has brought together five municipalities (Malmö, Dresden, Rome, Messina, and Utrecht).

As part of EURESFO24, an [interactive workshop](#) was organised to address the key questions:

- How can local governments design and implement *citizen engagement in climate resilience/adaptation* planning and implementation, especially to involve the most vulnerable groups in society?
- How to do so in a meaningful and effective way, beyond just “ticking the box of participation”, considering substantial resource constraints imposed on local governments?

Each case was facilitated by local experts and drew on insights from the Adaptation AGORA, UrbanReLeaf, and ACCTING projects.

Participants explored the challenges, strategies, and best practices for fostering inclusive participation and community engagement in co-creating local adaptation solutions, tailored to the specific needs and constraints of each context. The Forum provided a valuable opportunity for the Adaptation AGORA Project to connect not only with other initiatives focused on citizen involvement in climate adaptation, but also to bring together diverse local and regional governments. This

interaction marked the beginning of a peer network that continued to collaborate through online peer-learning events.

Discussion and feedback

Key recommendations to local practitioners for the effective inclusion of vulnerable groups in climate adaptation planning and implementation:

- Recognize and understand the multidimensional, intersectional character of vulnerability

Vulnerability is driven by different factors such as age, health, housing situation, socio-economic status, legal status, literacy or language.

- Work with intermediaries and cultural mediators to engage most vulnerable communities

Many organisations (service providers, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), community-led initiatives, workers unions, medical services, to neighbourhood centres and ambassadors) already engage with vulnerable populations and they can provide access, legitimacy and knowledge of needs.

- Collect and use data in creative ways: go where the people are

The data is sometimes hard to access, due to privacy concerns or lack of capacity from the part of local governments. A creative approach could be to meet the people you want to engage with at their own time, space and pace.

- Reframe from “vulnerable” to “valuable” people

Those people who are most exposed to climate hazards like heat might also have the most experience with developing creative solutions and approaches to deal with them. These capacities should be recognized and fostered.

- Building and keeping trust is imperative

Strategies to build trust and legitimacy are early involvement of the people in the process, transparency about the objective, timeline and (non-)impact of any participatory process, engagement with local groups, already active on the territory, use public space for public engagement.

- Build municipal capacity for meaningful & long-term citizen engagement across silos

Municipalities and their staff need the financial resources, capacities and mandate to make citizen engagement an integral part of their work.

- Design participatory processes with inclusivity & reciprocity at the core

Inclusivity throughout the planning & implementation of participatory processes - from communicating in various languages, to offering childcare and fair compensation, or using power-sensitive facilitation techniques.

Material availability

Details on the workshop are available here <https://sustainablejustcities.eu/resources/euresfo-workshop-report-co-creating-inclusive-climate-adaptation-solutions>

More information about a series of peer-to-peer learning online sessions specific to each Pilot, which were kicked-off by this event, can be found in the [Adaptation AGORA D5.2](#) and on the Agora Community Hub (Rome, Malmö, Aragón Pilot, Dresden).

3.2.4 Peer-learning workshop 4

Topic

Three main topics were addressed during the workshop: Contextual factors and enabling environment for citizen engagement, knowledge transmission, and designing a citizen engagement initiative.

The meeting was held online via Microsoft Teams on 13 December 2024. All the details are available in the Adaptation AGORA D1.2.

Participants and stakeholders

Total number of participants: 20

The participants were 6 external experts, and 14 members of the Adaptation AGORA consortium.

Methodology of engagement/invitation

An open invitation was sent to the Adaptation AGORA community and the experts who were interviewed or provided survey responses for T1.2.

Format and methodology

The workshop employed a participatory and interactive approach, using the Miro online whiteboard as a central collaborative tool. This digital platform facilitated real-time engagement, enabling participants to visualize ideas, co-develop concepts, and contribute to shared outputs. The methodology was designed to promote discursive participation, drawing on principles of deliberative democracy where open dialogue, critical reflection, and consensus-building were prioritized. The process was structured into a series of sessions and relied on supporting slides in which first the content of the discussion was presented, and then the discussions moved to the Miro board. Each of the three topics presented had a clear objective and guiding instructions:

- Ice-breaker session: Where would you situate your expertise, and about which topic are you more eager to discuss about?

- Topic A: Contextual factors and enabling environment for citizen engagement
- Topic B: Knowledge transmission
- Topic C: Designing a citizen engagement initiative

The workshop agenda was designed to balance structured activities with open-ended reflection and group discussion. After the initial icebreaker to foster rapport and familiarity with the Miro functionalities, participants engaged in the thematic sessions focused on the key aspects of citizen engagement that emerged during the interviews. This methodological approach ensured that both the process and outcomes of deliberation were valued, with an emphasis on inclusivity and collaborative decision-making.

Discussion and feedback

The three stages of the workshop produced different discussion and results. First, the workshop highlighted how participants felt different contextual factors affected engagement, and whether it was possible to control for these when designing engagement activities. The second part of the workshop identified the pathways and mechanisms for citizen engagement knowledge transfer between key actors. The final section sought to bring all the prior knowledge together and create a novel way of conveying this via a serious game that focused on the choices and trade-offs when designing a citizen engagement initiative.

Material availability

Adaptation AGORA D1.2 <https://adaptationagora.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/Deliverable-D1.2-Report-on-the-methodologies-and-recommendations-used-for-citizen-engagement.pdf>

3.3 Final conference: Citizens Together for Climate Adaptation

The activities carried out throughout the deployment of T6.3 were expected to conclude with a final conference under the title 'Citizens Together for Climate Adaptation' which would involve at least 4 other relevant projects (e.g. I-CHANGE) to present various approaches towards involving citizens in climate change actions. Furthermore, the event was intended to involve Climate Pact Ambassadors (CPA), to broaden the perspectives and discussion that could be generated during the meeting.

Initially in the GA it was stated that the consortium would seek to organize the event back-to-back with European Climate Change Adaptation Conference (ECCA) 2023 or ECCA 2025 to ensure mass participation. However, given the development of the interactions with different stakeholder groups within Adaptation AGORA, the increasing interest from diverse target audiences and the willingness from stakeholders located in different regions to partake in online events and discussions, this was re-evaluated.

Firstly, ECCA2023 would have taken place too early in the project to carry out a final conference. Secondly, when considering ECCA2025 it was evidenced that many of the projects and stakeholders that would be interested and able to benefit from this activity, as well as significantly contributing to the discussion, would not be present in the event. Hence, it was deemed more appropriate to carry out the event in an online format, involving four Horizon Europe projects with valuable insights and allowing stakeholders to participate regardless of their physical location.

This transition from the initial idea detailed in the GA and the final proposal was evaluated jointly with the Project Management Team of Adaptation AGORA and approved by the Project Officer.

The title of the event was 'Citizens Together for Climate Adaptation' and it was held online via Microsoft Teams on 11 November 2025, between 10:00 and 12:00 CET.

Figure 7. Advertisement of the Adaptation AGORA final event “Citizens together for climate adaptation”.

The conference was organized to summarise the outputs and results of all the previous networking events. It was the chance to show the outputs and results of the Adaptation AGORA project, to connect them to the activities of other European projects, to nurture future cooperations also after the project end, and to get feedback by different stakeholders including CPAs and Partners. CPAs and members of the four projects’ consortium were invited to get inspiration and support related to climate policies, to get a strong connection with local communities and organizations with valuable perspectives on practical, inclusive climate solutions, and to amplify the message through new networks.

Participants and stakeholders

Total number of registered participants: 208

Total number of attendees: 76 (out of which 4 Climate Pact Ambassadors)

Three types of audiences were mainly represented during the webinar: Academia, civil society, and Government. Details of registered participants:

- Local Communities: 9
- Academia and Research: 105
- Governments and Decision-Makers: 26
- Civil Society: 36
- Citizens/Public Opinion: 11
- Investors: 3
- Media: 2
- Consortium Partners and EC project Officers: 16

Methodology of engagement/invitation

The webinar was advertised on the Adaptation AGORA website, Adaptation AGORA social media pages, Adaptation AGORA partners' social media pages (Facebook and LinkedIn), Adaptation AGORA partners' newsletters, and through direct invitations by email using the Adaptation AGORA email account.

The webinar was conducted in English. A registration form was created using Microsoft Forms and kept open for four weeks. An invitation letter, to be shared via email with the target audience, was prepared with two different messages: one addressed to Climate Pact Ambassadors and Climate Pact Partners, and the other sent to stakeholders who had previously been involved with Adaptation AGORA's past activities. The link to the event was sent in a separate email the day before the event. This email also served as a reminder for participants.

Potential participants contacted the Adaptation AGORA team by email just before the start of the webinar and during the webinar to join, but this was not possible due to the security settings. Email accounts needed to be carefully monitored to avoid unwanted participants (such as hackers).

Format and methodology

The event was organized by Adaptation AGORA and co-organised by other four EU projects: I-CHANGE (<https://ichange-project.eu/>), CLIMAS (<https://www.climas-project.eu/>), PRO-CLIMATE (<https://pro-climate.eu/>) and NEUROCLIMA (<https://neuroclima.eu/>). The moderator, Nicola Loglisci, introduced the event and then invited the project coordinators to briefly present their respective projects (10 minutes each). Paola Mercogliano began by introducing Adaptation AGORA, followed by Rebecca Huetig who introduced CLIMAS, Antonio Parodi who introduced I-CHANGE,

and finally Iason Tamiakis and Barbara Gobbo, who introduced PRO-CLIMATE and NEUROCLIMA (they planned a joint activity).

The second part of the meeting was dedicated to practical activities using citizen engagement tools developed within the projects. The participants were divided into four breakout rooms:

- Room Adaptation AGORA
- Room CLIMAS
- Room PRO-CLIMATE&NEUROCLIMA
- Room I-CHANGE

Due to a technical issue, the CLIMAS room was unavailable, and the activity was conducted in the plenary room instead. After 30 minutes of practice in the breakout rooms, all participants reconvened in the plenary room to share feedback and discuss the results.

Topic

The general topic of the meeting was to convene different projects and stakeholders interested in citizen engagement for climate adaptation to show existing tools supporting this objective, to provide feedback, share ideas and to discuss future developments. Each breakout room addressed a different topic based on a citizen engagement tool developed during the project with the common objective of exploiting the tools themselves and to provide them a long-term impact. The topic of the rooms was chosen by the project partners considering the interactive level of the tool (which should be used during and after the event), the possibility that the tool could be shared by the stakeholders after the event, and the possibility that the activity could provide useful feedback to the projects and to the community.

Room Adaptation AGORA

Figure 8. Screenshot of the Adaptation AGORA Room presentation.

This session introduced the Adaptation AGORA Community Hub and its functionalities. The meeting focused on explaining how the hub can increase the visibility of climate adaptation projects, foster citizen engagement, and support collaboration across communities. Participants were guided through the platform's features, including the Adaptation Action Explorer, digital tools such as academies and mobile applications, discussion forums, and thematic areas like heat resilience and youth climate justice. Upcoming enhancements, such as an interactive glossary and direct messaging between members, were also highlighted.

The session demonstrated the process for uploading content and events, offering two options: a detailed back-end method and simplified online forms. Contributors are required to provide basic details, summaries, keywords, and structured sections such as an introduction, methodology, and key messages. The hub aims to amplify project visibility, encourage peer learning, and build capacity, while avoiding duplication of efforts.

Feedback from participants confirmed their interest in the platform's long-term sustainability, which was assured beyond the Adaptation AGORA project timeline. Registration flexibility was clarified, allowing individuals to join without official city affiliation. Participants also expressed the need for more time to explore the hub before identifying content gaps.

The session concluded with a call to action for participants to register, upload content and events, and share feedback on missing features or topics. Organisers committed to supporting users throughout the process and continuing to improve the hub based on the feedback received.

Room CLIMAS

Figure 9. Screenshot of the CLIMAS Room presentation.

The CLIMAS Toolbox navigation map helps users understand the tool at different stages of a climate assembly—at the beginning, during, and in the follow-up phase. The map incorporates design thinking methodologies and supporting materials, offering an overview of how the tools were developed. Some tools are still being finalised, so users are encouraged to revisit the site for updates.

After exploring the tools and materials, participants are invited to provide feedback on how the CLIMAS Toolbox is presented and how dissemination efforts can better target relevant stakeholders. A customised business model canvas is available on the Miro board, where participants are asked to focus on the customer segments to identify potential users and audiences for the toolbox. Suggested categories include academia, local authorities, NGOs focused on citizen participation and climate adaptation, cities, regions, EU institutions, and climate assembly organisers. Examples such as Fridays for Future and specific regions, like Italian islands and Belgium, are mentioned to inspire discussion.

The goal is to gather expert input on which stakeholders should be prioritised for communication and dissemination, and to receive honest feedback on the toolbox itself, its tools, and its presentation. This will help improve the deployment and use of the Toolbox in climate assemblies.

Room PRO-CLIMATE&NEUROCLIMA

Figure 10. Screenshot of the PRO-CLIMATE&NEUROCLIMA Room presentation.

This session focused on collaboration between the PRO-CLIMATE and NEUROCLIMA projects. It began with an introduction to NEUROCLIMA, explaining that the project aims to foster systemic and behavioural transformation for climate resilience through an AI-powered 'nervous system'. This system connects stakeholders, policymakers, institutions, and citizens using digital and participatory tools such as AI-driven search, conversational bots, learning platforms, and deliberation spaces. The goal is to translate complex climate data into actionable insights, strengthen democratic

engagement, and accelerate behavioural change. NEUROCLIMA integrates artificial intelligence, data analysis, and participatory processes, and will be tested through pilots in multiple countries to validate both the technical architecture and behavioural models.

PRO-CLIMATE’s approach addresses both human and systemic barriers to adaptation. The discussion highlighted common obstacles such as distrust, apathy, and institutional silos, stressing the importance of combining top-down and bottom-up approaches. The session explored how behavioural change processes can be initiated and sustained beyond project timelines, aiming for long-term impact on governance and community engagement. Participants then engaged in a collaborative exercise using a Miro board to co-design a living lab scenario.

They selected a case study of a coastal town facing flash floods, erosion, and sea-level rise, identifying key stakeholders including municipal authorities, emergency services, local businesses, port authorities, citizen associations, schools, and research institutions. The group discussed barriers such as public fatigue and lack of trust, proposing actions such as participatory workshops, vulnerability mapping, citizen assemblies, and the creation of a local climate office or a dedicated adaptation officer to ensure continuity and credibility. The importance of political endorsement and sustained engagement beyond the project duration was repeatedly emphasised.

The session concluded with agreement on the need for inclusive processes, clear governance structures, and practical tools to foster behavioural change and improve climate adaptation strategies. Participants suggested combining participatory design, data-driven reflection, and institutional support to create lasting impact. Time constraints prevented full completion of the exercise, but the intention was to continue refining ideas and report back with a summary of proposed actions.

I-CHANGE

Figure 11. Screenshot of the I-CHANGE Room presentation.

This session introduced the board game 'Our Climate Story,' developed under the I-CHANGE project to engage players, particularly young audiences, in understanding how daily choices influence emissions, risks, and community resilience. The game was co-designed with living labs and demonstrated using the Bologna map, which includes local landmarks and streets to create a realistic city environment.

The game aims to combine learning and action by having players navigate their city, make sustainable choices, and collaborate to reduce CO₂ emissions. It uses printed materials, including player cards representing different roles, place cards indicating destinations, CO₂ cards for emissions, risk cards for hazards like heatwaves and pollution, and solution cards for actions such as green roofs or early warning systems. The currency in the game is represented by leaves, symbolising sustainable resources.

Players start from a public transport station and move across the board to visit assigned locations while managing emissions. Movement options include walking, cycling, public transport, or driving, each with different costs in leaves and CO₂ impact. Walking and cycling produce no emissions, while public transport and driving increase CO₂ and require spending leaves. If the climate scenario scale reaches the red zone, all players lose, emphasising collective responsibility. Players can earn community leaves by cleaning waste or choosing eco-friendly travel and use them to implement solutions collaboratively.

The educational value lies in simulating real-world challenges and encouraging discussion about decisions and their consequences. After the game, participants reflect on which choices led to higher emissions and which solutions were most effective. The game is suitable for ages ten and above, including secondary school students, and can also be used in municipal events. Materials are free to download, and users can adapt the game for their own cities. There was interest in accessing vector files for customisation and suggestions to incorporate future urban mobility plans into the game design. The session concluded with appreciation for the concept and its potential for educational and participatory use.

Discussion and feedback

During the discussion phase, several pieces of constructive feedback emerged from the breakout rooms, with an emphasis on collaboration and actionable ideas.

Adaptation AGORA

Feedback from participants confirmed their interest in the platform's long-term sustainability, which has been assured beyond the Adaptation AGORA project timeline.

CLIMAS

The discussion centred on dissemination and exploitation efforts for the CLIMAS Toolbox and related tools. The tools are designed to assist local communities and those interested in establishing

citizen assemblies on climate. Assemblies should be inclusive, representative, and capable of influencing local policies on climate sustainability.

The tools have been developed to help participants create, maintain, evaluate, and follow up on climate assemblies, so any feedback on who could benefit most from these tools, and who to target in dissemination efforts, is greatly appreciated.

PRO-CLIMATE & NEUROCLIMA

An important conversation emerged about creating a local officer role specialised in climate change. This role would serve as a link between citizens, civil society, and municipal authorities, and was suggested as a necessary action for climate change adaptation and behavioural change.

I-CHANGE

The board game was beneficial but challenging to play in just half an hour, so it would be preferable to extend the playing time step by step. It was suggested that participants download and print the materials to try the game themselves.

The main points raised during the discussion were:

- The age suitability (the game is suitable for ages 10+, ideal for middle school students or those aged 15+).
- It could be useful to provide materials for other/new cities.
- Updating the board to reflect differences or future mobility plans in cities.

Material availability

The material (recordings, presentations) will be shared as soon as they have been collected.

3.4 Other synergies

The information reported in this section complement what is also reported in the Adaptation AGORA D6.4 (“Communication and dissemination report”) and D6.5 (“Exploitation Strategy: Adaptation AGORA outcomes and results”). Adaptation AGORA actively fostered collaborations that significantly amplified its visibility and impact. A central partnership was established with the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change, which provided access to dedicated resources and extensive outreach capabilities.

This collaboration included the co-organization of numerous events, leveraging MIP4Adapt’s logistical support and broad stakeholder network. Regular monthly meetings within the Mission’s thematic working group ensured continuous engagement and positioned Adaptation AGORA at the forefront of adaptation efforts in Europe. Since the beginning of 2024 the Adaptation AGORA team have been members of the MIP4Adapt Citizen and Stakeholder Engagement Thematic Working Group, with a member of SEI Oxford acting as one of the champions of the group.

The Group met on a regular basis (often monthly) and worked to produce a briefing note output that can be found here: [“\[TWG Output\] Briefing Note - Improving Collaboration and Experience Sharing of Citizen & Stakeholder Engagement Approaches for Climate Adaptation | Futurium”](#) and the Adaptation AGORA results were presented in the [“How changing the behaviours of citizens can make climate adaptation more effective”](#) event organised by MIP4Adapt in October 2025.

Beyond these strategic alliances, Adaptation AGORA’s outputs became foundational for several Horizon Europe projects. For instance, SCIENCEUS adopted Adaptation AGORA’s citizen engagement protocols (workshops, focus groups, and surveys) along with its communication tools to strengthen outreach initiatives. Similarly, TICCA4DANU integrated Adaptation AGORA’s methodologies and digital tools to address climate risks in the Danube region, while The HuT applied Adaptation AGORA’s stakeholder engagement approaches to improve extreme event management across Europe.

The TRIGGER project drew inspiration from Adaptation AGORA’s work with socially vulnerable groups to design Climate Health Connection Labs, and LIQUIDICE used the project’s results as a baseline for policy and stakeholder engagement strategies. Another notable synergy was with SystR, which builds on Adaptation AGORA’s science-policy nexus work, citizen engagement methods, and policy analysis to propose innovative solutions for systemic risks.

Adaptation AGORA’s influence extended beyond Horizon Europe projects to other initiatives and regional spin-offs. The bePrepARed Interreg project between Italy and Croatia incorporated the Adaptation AGORA’s outputs, while the ROCCIA project in Rome emerged as a direct spin-off from pilot activities, supporting local adaptation strategies. Similarly, the HeatSafe project in Malmö continues Adaptation AGORA’s work on heatwave vulnerability and resilience. Additional collaborations, such as SRACC-Camp Adapt in Campania, replicate Adaptation AGORA’s methodologies to design regional adaptation strategies.

I-CHANGE relied on the Adaptation AGORA final event to disseminate the board game developed during the project’s life, while CLIMAS took advantage of the Adaptation AGORA co-organized event to get inputs for the final exploitation pathway section of the final Communication Dissemination and Exploitation plan.

These synergies demonstrate that Adaptation AGORA’s legacy will endure well beyond its official end of the project. The citizen engagement mapping, pilot protocols, and capacity-building initiatives have become valuable resources for decision-makers, scientists, and practitioners, ensuring that the project’s results continue to shape climate adaptation efforts across Europe.

Other activities were co-organised during the project’s life with other EU projects:

- Joint meeting in Arenzano June 2023 – Adaptation AGORA Milestone 7 (I-CHANGE)
- Joint presentation at Italian Society for Climate Science (SISC) Conference, November 2023 (I-CHANGE)

- Joint citizen science event series (Valbormida), February 2024 (I-CHANGE)
- Joint session at EGU General Assembly, April 2024 (I-CHANGE)
- Joint presentation at the Plinius Conference, October 2024 (I-CHANGE)
- Joint session at EGU General Assembly April 2025, (I-CHANGE, TRIGGER)
- Joint citizen science event series (Valbormida), February 2025 (I-CHANGE)

4. Conclusions

Adaptation AGORA has emerged as a catalyst for systemic change in climate resilience across Europe. From its inception, the project positioned itself not merely as a research initiative but as a driver of collaboration, knowledge transfer, and policy integration.

The project's impact began with its pilot activities, which served as living laboratories for citizen engagement and co-creation. These pilots generated validated methodologies and digital tools that quickly attracted attention beyond the consortium. Horizon Europe projects integrated AGORA's protocols and Information and Communication Tool (ICT) solutions into their frameworks, while regional projects extended the legacy at local level. This ripple effect demonstrates how Adaptation AGORA's outputs became foundational for new initiatives tackling climate risks in diverse contexts.

Synergies flourished through strategic alliances. The project actively collaborated with the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change, leveraging platforms like MIP4Adapt and thematic working groups to amplify its methodologies. The creation of the Agora Community Hub offered resources, discussion forums, and interactive features to support collaboration among stakeholders ensuring that knowledge exchange would continue well beyond the project's lifetime, linking practitioners, policymakers, and civil society in a dynamic digital ecosystem.

Policy influence was another cornerstone of Adaptation AGORA's strategy (Adaptation AGORA D6.5). Through high-level events such as COP30, Adaptation Futures, and the ESA Living Planet Symposium, the project positioned its findings at the heart of global climate dialogues. Its Roadmap for Transformational Change and policy briefs provided actionable recommendations for embedding citizen engagement into governance structures, offering decision-makers a clear pathway to institutionalize participatory approaches.

In essence, Adaptation AGORA bridged science, policy, and society to accelerate Europe's journey toward climate resilience demonstrating the critical role of collaboration and participatory approaches in advancing climate adaptation strategies across Europe. By fostering synergies among EU-funded projects, research institutions, policymakers, and citizens, Adaptation AGORA created a dynamic and inclusive environment for knowledge exchange and co-creation. This collaborative framework was operationalized through a series of webinars, peer-learning workshops, and a final conference, all of which served as platforms for dialogue, capacity-building, and dissemination of best practices. The project successfully connected diverse stakeholders, including local authorities, NGOs, academia, and citizen groups, ensuring that climate adaptation efforts were not isolated but

integrated within broader European initiatives. Partnerships with other European projects amplified the project's reach and impact, while the participation in thematic working groups like MIP4Adapt reinforced its role in shaping EU-level strategies.

In person engagements (e.g. EURESFO24, ESA's Living Planet Symposium, COP30) wove Adaptation AGORA's methods into the routines of communities and institutions.

Peer learning workshops were the engine of mutual capacity building, internal and external sessions produced materials and published outputs that codified what works in citizen engagement. This commitment to honest learning strengthened the credibility of Adaptation AGORA's methods and offered replicable frameworks for other projects.

Strategic synergies multiplied the project's footprint. Collaboration threads ran through MIP4Adapt's thematic working groups, and a long list of Horizon Europe projects, with joint events, platform mentions, and reciprocal dissemination. MIP4Adapt repeatedly showcased the project's achievements ensuring the project's results were visible where Mission Adaptation practitioners convene. These relationships actively carried Adaptation AGORA's tools and protocols into new settings, priming replication and scaling.

Adaptation AGORA's greatest impact was inclusion. The consortium prioritized marginalized cohorts (elderly citizens, people with disabilities, immigrants, outdoor workers, youth, and, remarkably, persons under custodial sentences) bringing voices rarely heard in EU-funded research and innovation into the heart of adaptation dialogues. These "positive deviations" reshaped methods and outputs, yielding insights that are both ethically vital and operationally valuable for cities seeking just resilience.

The project highlighted that effective climate adaptation requires active involvement of citizens in decision-making processes. Through participatory methodologies—such as focus groups, climate assemblies, and citizen science initiatives. Adaptation AGORA empowered communities to co-design solutions tailored to local vulnerabilities. Engagement strategies emphasized diversity and inclusion, ensuring representation of youth, multi-ethnic communities, and vulnerable groups. Trust-building emerged as a cornerstone for sustained participation, supported by transparent communication and continuity mechanisms beyond the project lifecycle.

One of project's most significant contributions was the successful integration of citizen-driven recommendations into local policy frameworks. Examples include Malmö's Urban Heat Strategy and Rome's Climate Strategy, which incorporated findings from the pilots. This demonstrates the potential of participatory approaches to influence governance and accelerate adaptation measures. However, sustaining these impacts requires institutional commitment, adequate resources, and mechanisms for ongoing citizen involvement.

The project demonstrated that inclusive and participatory approaches are essential for designing and implementing climate adaptation strategies that reflect local priorities and vulnerabilities.

Trust-building, education, and continuity mechanisms emerged as critical factors for sustaining citizen involvement beyond project timelines. The integration of digital tools, citizen science initiatives, and co-creation methodologies strengthened the link between scientific knowledge and community action, while the collaboration with other Horizon Europe projects and thematic working groups enhanced visibility, impact, and long-term sustainability of the initiatives.

Annex A: Meeting protocol

Webinars promotion

The webinars should be promoted in large advance (possibly 2 months earlier). Posts on the website and on the social media channels should be shared first, followed by a reminder in proximity of the event date. WP6 will produce a promotional card, stating the most relevant information.

WP6 will produce a promotional card (see example below), stating the most relevant information.

Sharing invitations

Invitations should be shared also by email to stakeholders that are identified as most relevant, using AGORA official project email. If you would like to invite someone you know well, you can send a second, personal, e-mail. The list of invited people must be uploaded, and updated with the names of the confirmed participants, on SharePoint. Please note that only public email addresses can be collected on the share point. Also, we cannot contact private email addresses using the project email account (it will result in “sharing sensitive data with a third party”).

Registration form

Organizers must create a registration form, respecting the tone of voice and the visual identity of the project. A recommended tool is Microsoft Forms. The registration form needs to be shared with the invited people via e-mail, website, or social media post. The following information must be included:

- Name
- Surname
- E-mail address
- Declaration of age
- Acceptance of Adaptation AGORA privacy policies.

More information can be asked, but there is no need to be mandatory.

Registrations for the events should be closed a couple of days in advance, to allow organizers to check and verify email addresses (and potentially exclude fake accounts). Only the clear/checked accounts will receive the link + password to join the event.

To create a new registration form, please take inspiration from the following <https://forms.office.com/e/4b5T70nitg>

Selection of the tool

Adaptation AGORA project recommends the utilization of Microsoft Teams, that allows splitting into rooms. Its new versions “Teams New”, foresees several features, including automatic transcriptions.

It is highly recommended to always use the latest version of Teams. The utilization of other platforms must be authorized by the coordinator.

Settings of the tool

Administrators and co-administrators

A certain number of admins from the Consortium should be identified, with the aim of having backups in case of need. Specific roles should also be identified before the start of the event.

Specific settings

The following settings are valid for any utilized tool:

- Private event (Access to the event is guaranteed only to those that received the participation link and password. This setting does not allow the sharing of the access credentials)
- Enable: "Enable waiting room"
- Disable: "Enable participation before host"
- Activate the option: "Deactivate participants upon entry"
- Enable: "Only authenticated users can join"
- Turn off screen sharing for participants
- Disable "File Transfer" to prevent sharing of malwares or viruses

The following option is not mandatory but recommended:

- Lock the session once participants have joined: "Manage Participants" > "More" (at the bottom of the panel) > "Lock Meeting"

Video

The video is active only for the speakers/presenters and moderators.

Audio

Active for both presenters/moderators and organizers (to allow communication in case of need).

Chat

The chat can be:

- 1) Activated from the very beginning
- 2) Activated only during the question-answer time slot
- 3) Kept closed

Audience can also share questions by using the “raise hands” button.

There are no good or bad options, it depends on the level of security that we want to achieve.

Practical test

A test should be done before the start of the event (on the same day or during the previous days) possibly simulating the same conditions under which the event will be run (same pc, same internet connection, same microphones, etc.).

Management of potential issues

- Any infiltrators under a false name/email who display inappropriate behaviour via chat or audio will be blocked and expelled.
- Any disrespectful comments shared via chat will be deleted.
- Users will not be able to share their screen or access video. They will only be able to share audio with permission from the organizers.
- In the case of a cyber-attack (losing control of the platform), the webinar needs to be interrupted immediately.

In case of need with the settings of Microsoft Teams, please contact APRE personnel:

santaniello@apre.it and mingardi@apre.it

Annex B: Q&A session for Webinar n°1

This is the transcription of the Q&A session.

1. Q: How comparable are the data between the ARPA stations and the Citizen Science stations if the instruments used are different? And how reliable are the latter if they are not regularly calibrated and checked?

A: This is a fundamental question in the context of using these kinds of data, and essentially, the approach we are trying to implement is as follows. The basic assumption is that an official and authorised station — such as those operated by ARPA, whether in Liguria, Veneto, or Piedmont — represents the so-called ground truth, the reference pivot. What is typically done is to compare, over long-time horizons — at least several seasons or years — the performance of the Citizen Science stations against the authoritative ones, and to assess whether the differences fall within one or more standard deviations. This kind of analysis is meaningful when considering at least seasonal averages. However, extreme events can challenge this assumption. Take, for instance, the episode in Genoa: if we had compared the ARPAL station, which recorded 200 mm, with the nearby Citizen Science station that measured 480 mm, our initial reaction might have been to assume that the Citizen Science station was wrong. But another important aspect comes into play here — the need for a multi-source assessment. That is precisely what we did: we used data from other nearby

Citizen Science stations, compared readings at a five-minute temporal resolution, and incorporated information from satellite and radar sensors. This analysis revealed that, in that specific case those stations happened to be directly beneath the most intense convective cell. So, despite appearing anomalous relative to the authorised network, they had in fact captured the most extreme part of the event. There is therefore no single, predefined recipe; rather, a set of techniques exists to increase confidence in such networks over time. Of course, caution is always required, but algorithms are available to detect potential drifts in the performance of stations — for instance, a gradual divergence in temperature readings. When such deviations are identified, the affected stations are removed from the database, and only a validated historical record is retained.

2. Q: Could you please elaborate on the crowdsourcing of landslide phenomena?

A: Yes, with the understanding that, for anyone interested, we could also share the contacts of the people we are collaborating with there. The process has essentially been as follows: extreme events, even historical ones, can leave visible marks on the morphological fabric of a slope or even on the urban landscape — changes in landforms that can still be recognised over time. Together with colleagues from the CNR in Perugia, we carried out an educational activity in schools in the eastern Liguria area, specifically in Chiavari, where that extreme hailstorm took place. While hail fortunately does not directly cause landslides, the initiative involved engaging students in visiting parts of the city affected by past extreme or flood events, talking to residents who still live there, and then using an open-access app that can also be applied elsewhere. In fact, it would be wonderful if, through this forum, interest emerged in using the same approach in other areas — to identify, through modern photographic tools, the impacted sites, georeference them, provide a first-level classification of the landslide area and its approximate size, and collect everything into a shared database. This database is later validated as part of the educational process — teaching students how to conduct field observations, refine their assessments, and thus gain their first experience in professional-level environmental monitoring. In this way, the initiative not only enriches local knowledge on landslide phenomena but also builds scientific capacity among young people. The app, accessible from both tablets and smartphones, allows users to perform this entire operation. For those interested, we would be happy to share it and test it together — as all such tools are, of course, continuously evolving and open to improvement.

3. Q: What kind of technical features and devices does the MeteoTracker app have?

A: The MeteoTracker is a sensor that we have available in a certain number of units, which we share both within the I-CHANGE project and for activities under AGORA. It is a compact device that can be attached to the roof of a car using magnets or fastened to a backpack or bicycle with a strap. It works together with a dedicated app and website, and as a person moves, it continuously collects data on temperature, pressure, and humidity. The device itself is very lightweight, the app consumes minimal battery power, and — just to give you an idea — on those buses I showed you

earlier, we installed the app about five months ago, and it's still running perfectly well. So, even in terms of energy impact, it's quite marginal.

4. Q: Does the I-CHANGE project concern only the city of Genoa, or are there similar initiatives in other Italian cities or regions where Citizen Science activities do not yet exist?

A: The I-CHANGE project is also active in other Italian cities, specifically in Bologna. Nothing prevents, within the cooperative framework between I-CHANGE and Adaptation AGORA, and through the concept of the Digital Agora, from initiating similar activities in other cities. This is particularly feasible because all the communication and educational materials developed over the past few years for the city of Genoa can easily be applied elsewhere. There is a website where these resources can be downloaded and freely used. If there were the capacity to create a critical mass and to secure some funding sources, it would even be possible to develop a more structured initiative. However, such an activity could also begin almost immediately — as soon as contact is established. There would be absolutely no problem in doing something similar; on the contrary, it would represent another important and highly valuable impact.

5. Q: Given the importance of meteorological data, don't you think there are too few weather balloons for data collection?

A: Indeed, launching a weather balloon into the atmosphere is quite an expensive operation if it is carried out several times a day, every day. Over the years, the Italian Air Force, for reasons beyond our control, has gradually reduced the frequency of these launches. It is also true that other monitoring techniques are becoming more established — not necessarily less costly, but different. For example, some companies now perform meteorological drone measurements, reaching altitudes of up to 5,000 metres to obtain vertical atmospheric profiles. Meanwhile, the European Space Agency (ESA) has developed a project to conduct electromagnetic radio soundings. However, I agree with you that having more weather balloons would not be a bad idea at all. There are, at present, other techniques that allow for atmospheric profiling using satellite data, such as GNSS-based methods, which can achieve measurements with an accuracy comparable to that of balloon soundings.

6. Q: I would like to ask for your reflection on how direct the link truly is between social change and political change in the current Italian context.

A: The hope is to foster greater awareness among the younger generations, so that one day, when they come to vote — if there is an adequate political and social alternative — they may choose something different. I often give the example of a boy from a small town in Liguria who, at the end of one of our seminars, said to me: “Antonio, you've convinced me that climate change is a real problem — and you've convinced all 21 of my classmates too. Now we'll go home and involve our families, that makes about 80 people, and then we'll go out and reach the other 8 billion.” Well, he was perhaps a little optimistic — but that's exactly the spirit. The idea is to one day achieve a greater collective awareness, one that will ultimately translate into voting differently, because change is

possible — and it can be achieved sustainably. I'll conclude with the issue of retrofitting our housing stock to make it more energy-efficient and sustainable. The European funds are available.

7. Q: How complex and distant is the stage at which the data collected through these initiatives could feed into early warning systems, and what could be the role of Citizen Science in the dissemination of alerts?

A: Both projects — AGORA, first and foremost, and I-CHANGE, closely following — have a strong technological dimension, understood as the ability to collect observational data not merely for awareness-raising or dissemination purposes, but for practical use. I-CHANGE features a data storage system in which information is archived, verified, and quality-checked. Our dream in the drawer, before the project's conclusion, is to be able to use these data — certainly those from voluntary ground-based stations, but hopefully also those from the mobile network — to feed nowcasting chains, that is, very short-term forecasting models. It is not a simple task, because, as those working in meteorological modelling say, “garbage in means garbage out.” If the input data are not properly validated and controlled, the model can become unstable. Nevertheless, our ambition is to move towards a stage where Citizen Science data can inform very short-term forecasting and early warning systems. And I believe we are not far from that point. I sincerely hope that within the timeframe of I-CHANGE and AGORA, we will begin to see concrete results — and that, on a future occasion, we will be able to present them. I am very optimistic about this.

8. Q: Have you ever happened to identify a malfunction in ARPA stations by detecting significant discrepancies coming from Citizen Science measurements?

A: not yet.

9. Q: I see on the MeteoTracker website that the instruments can be purchased, and that the cost is not insignificant. Are there any funds or initiatives planned to distribute these devices more widely and effectively?

A: The cost is not negligible — we're talking about roughly €150, so it's not insignificant, comparable to a low-end mobile phone. Of course, it depends a great deal on one's level of enthusiasm for this kind of activity, but it's certainly not a trivial expense. What we did, for instance, within the I-CHANGE project, was to provide these sensors to citizens who committed to a certain level of engagement in collecting data — and, in the end, we gave them the devices. This is a model that can be replicated elsewhere. The European Commission is increasingly funding projects that promote citizen empowerment using such sensors — the idea being that we give you the device, and you contribute by collecting data. If you contact us by email, we can discuss this in more detail — and we might even have a few devices left, if you're willing to take a bike ride and collect some data!

10. Q: Is there any relationship between Citizen Science for air quality and the IQR instruments?

A: Not that I'm aware of, but it's not the area we've focused on the most, as we're not experts on the subject. In the I-CHANGE project, it was the University of Bologna that worked on that aspect.

11. Q: Is it still possible to take part in and join the Citizen Science project to collect data?

A: yes, it is.

12. Q: As members of a hiking federation, could we define the reliability levels you require to borrow or rent the measurement devices?

A: We also have a partnership with the Italian Alpine Club (CAI). This collaboration has, for example, led to the installation of a new weather station along the Alta Via dei Monti Liguri, which is expected to become part of the so-called "Climate Trails" promoted by CAI. Among the CAI groups, we are working particularly closely with the Arenzano branch. These members go on hikes while collecting environmental data. For instance, in March last year, they went trekking in the Cuneo mountains area and recorded a temperature anomaly of around 10°C above the climatological average on the 11th of March. These are exactly the kinds of data we are interested in. So, when we talk about people who go hiking, that already gives us a kind of reliability guarantee: if you simply remember to attach the sensor and collect the data, that is already a significant added value for us — and it would also help cover an area that is fairly well documented, though not yet fully enriched.

Annex C: Q&A session for Webinar n°3

The Q&A session was particularly lively, demonstrating strong engagement from the international audience. Here the transcription of the Q&A session.

1. Q: Could you please share the QR code for the project again

A: Please find out more about Adaptation AGORA at www.adaptationagora.eu.

2. Q: I'm Sofia studying Master of Climate Change in Italy. I want to know if I want to work in this field, what is the pathway or if there is any job opportunity.

A: Please contact our PM

3. Q: for Judith: how much time passed between the 3 meetings with stakeholders? thanks!

A: Approx. 6 months went by between the inception workshop (Q4 2023) and the intermediate focus groups (Q2 2024), and then another 6 months between those and the final workshop (Q1 2025)

4. Q: Could you talk about the impact created?

A: You can find more information about the Adaptation AGORA pilots at www.adaptationagora.eu.

5. Q: could you explain a bit how you identified and reached out to the different stakeholders to get them involved in the project?

A: Yes, we used the tool MapStakes to map and involve stakeholders. For more information, please visit: <https://www.sei.org/tools/mapstakes-tool-mapping-stakeholders/>. We were also in close contact with local partners to ensure that important interests were represented among stakeholders engaged in Adaptation AGORA.

6. Q: To Judith: Were citizens only involved in the focus groups or also in the other workshops?

A: Citizens were involved in all three events, the initial workshop, focus group activities (divided by target audiences as we explained) and the final workshops, both urban and rural

7. Q: Was there a systematic stakeholder analysis before the workshops / focus groups?

A: Yes, we used the tool MapStakes to map and involve stakeholders. For more information, please visit: <https://www.sei.org/tools/mapstakes-tool-mapping-stakeholders/>

8. Q: Related to that, how did you guarantee the legitimacy of the workshops / focus groups results?

A: We created a framework, which you can find in our website www.adaptationagora.eu to ensure legitimacy

9. Q: Was there a culture specific engagement? How do you cater to the varying cultural and language needs?

A: Yes, we cater to varying cultural and language needs and that is why we also created protocols linked to the specific case of focus group activities with multiethnic groups, you can find them in our website and in the Adaptation AGORA Zenodo Community

10. Q: How these time-constrained projects who aim to engage local communities and citizens plan to do so in the long period? After the projects funds end

A: In Malmö, we have secured new funding to continue our collaboration after Adaptation AGORA.

11. Q: Which recruitment process did you follow for involving stakeholders?

A: The objective was to gather interest and reach as many members of each target audience as possible; information was shared through specific stakeholder groups (associations, assemblies, partner organizations of the consortium, the city council, etc.) as well as massively through online channels.

12. Q: How did you approach multi-cultural communities?

A: In Malmö, multicultural communities were engaged through existing networks, specifically by connecting with participants at a weekly language café where non-Swedish speakers practice their language skills.

13. Q: How were the participants in the workshops summoned (how was the call made)? From that moment on, was communication maintained with them?

A: Participants were contacted via email and phone through existing networks and organizations. Ongoing communication ensured continuity, and the same individuals were invited to all workshops to foster lasting relationships.

14. Q: Was there a monetary incentive / reimbursement for participation of the citizens in the workshops and focus groups?

A: No, there were no incentives to ensure that citizens participated out of their own interest to contribute to climate change adaptation

15. Q: Why the groups in the project in Rome has been quite small?

A: All groups were of a similar size to allow stakeholders to freely share their thoughts as with larger groups it would have not been possible to gather everyone's opinion

16. Q: What is discussed in these focus groups and inception workshops? Is it something more like participatory planning, knowledge cocreation, or awareness building?

A: All the information can be found in the summaries we have shared through the Adaptation AGORA pilots at www.adaptationagora.eu

17. Q: Is there any monitoring that is done to test if former participants' ideas are implemented later?

A: Yes, we're following up with decision-makers, and we share the information with the direct stakeholders involve

18. Q: Did citizens have difficulties to focus on adaptation (as opposed to mitigation)? How did you tackle this challenge?

A: We made specific definitions at the beginning of each of the sessions we had together to ensure we could focus on adaptation

19. Q: is it possible to find documents or reports where all the initiatives by the pilots are explained more in detail? thank you

A: You can find more information about the Adaptation AGORA pilots at www.adaptationagora.eu.

20. Q: can you please tell us more about digital tools you have used? Were they integrated into the workshops/focus-groups/co-creation sessions?

A: We did not integrate the ICTs into the workshops as they were not a core part of our activities and they were developed concurrently, we will be doing specific activities during Q2, Q3 and Q4 with our stakeholders to present the ICTs. We have already for instance presented them to young adult cohorts in Spain and will be presenting them to members of Multinational Companies to gather their feedback.

21. Q: Could the Agora pilots be a little more specific about the extent to which the results of the co-creation process are reflected in policy decisions?

A: For instance, in Malmö, findings from Adaptation AGORA support the upcoming urban heat mitigation strategy and guide work on nature-based solutions; meanwhile in Rome the findings have been integrated in the Climate strategy presented during 2024 and being put into place during this year.

22. Q: Could some of you point out to the difficulties you faced in mobilizing collective action from communities?

A: Reaching individuals who may not trust the system and how their contributions will effectively be used, as you can see from the reports we've created (available at www.adaptationagora.eu) there is a lack of general trust from citizens in policies, so that was the first barrier to overcome.

23. Q: How do you address the lack of scientific knowledge among the communities? Were the workshops enough? Did you inculcate local/traditional wisdom?

A: We incorporated local/traditional wisdom, particularly in the case of the rural Pilot in Zaragoza citizens were eager to be the ones presenting part of the knowledge to urban residents, as they saw the lack of knowledge in those cohorts. In most cases we addressed the issue directly and provided a general framework after the inception workshop, as these served to understand what the real knowledge was the average citizens had on climate change risks and adaptation needs. These were great insights to plan the subsequent methodologies.

24. Q: How many citizens / stakeholders were involved in the different cities?

A: You can find more information about the Adaptation AGORA pilots at www.adaptationagora.eu.

25. Q: Anna V email details of the group activity you did where I saw people in a circle with string connecting them, it looked interesting george.cummings1@gmail.com

A: You can contact our PM

26. Q: Were there specific population groups / stakeholders that were very difficult to be involved? What were successful ways to get them involved?

A: Perhaps multiethnic groups were sometimes harder, and it was through associations of these specific stakeholders that we overcame the difficulty of reaching these cohorts and successfully engaged them in FG and final workshop activities.

27. Q: I study project management, and I have a specific interest on the ones on climate change, as AGORA. Which is the path to present a project like this?

A: You can find more about EU Projects in the EU's official website <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/programmes/horizon>

28. Q: Did participants occasionally stray into mitigation? Because excluding causal issues might seem somewhat arbitrary and counterintuitive to some?

A: Yes, there are some topics that are in between both, so we tackled them from the adaptation perspective and addressed secondary proposals from the mitigation side

29. Q: For the Malmo case: could you please provide more info on the "vulnerability walk" exercise? Sounds interesting

A: Thank you, for more information about the Vulnerability Walk please visit <https://weadapt.org/knowledge-base/assar/experiential-learning-vulnerability-walk/>

30. Q: what's the studying path to work on these projects?

A: You can find more about EU Projects in the EU's official website <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/programmes/horizon>

31. Q: Climate Assemblies: How did you communicate with the randomly selected citizens? Did the citizens confirm their interest in this "lottery" before being selected?

A: In each Climate Assembly organised with support from CLIMAS the random selection process followed the same two-step methodology of recruitment: First: sending out invitations to randomly chosen citizens. Citizens could then express their interest to participate in the assembly. Second: The organization team selected a diverse group of participants based on socio-demographic data provided by the citizens (e.g. age, gender, region of residence, attitude towards the topic). This means that not everyone who expressed interest in participating, was chosen as participant. For more information, please reach out for rebecca.hueting@dblue.it.

32. Q: How can we ensure that climate assemblies have concrete results? Could citizens get frustrated and lose heart if governments don't follow their recommendations?

A: This is a central challenge for (Climate) Citizens' Assemblies. To ensure their recommendations lead to real outcomes, it's crucial that governments and public administrations commit to a clear follow-up process before the assembly begins. One important step is for authorities to promise that, once they receive the recommendations, they will review each one individually and publicly explain whether they can implement it—and if not, why not. Additionally, holding regular follow-up events—such as after one year after the assembly—can help track progress, maintain transparency, and show citizens how their input is being used over time. Active NGOs, stakeholders, media and even former participants can also play a key role in keeping up public pressure and holding authorities accountable for putting the recommendations into practice.

33. Q: I am following a course on EDI (equality, diversity, inclusion). I can do 1-month internship. I would like to do it on AGORA or CLIMAS, who should I contact?

A: Please contact our PM info@climas-project.eu or rebecca.hueting@dblue.it

34. Q: In Riga, did I understand correctly that you used an app for the citizen science exercise? If yes, what was the name of the app?

A: The Citizen Science exercise was based on a local citizen science project called Dabasdati.lv. However, participants did not use the app; instead, they carried out an activity following our Citizen Science Toolkit, which is currently in its prototype version. The toolkit is a guidance document that will soon be published in its final form on the CLIMAS website. For a more detailed overview of its contents, please contact julian.vicens@eurecat.org.

